

ATTENTION TO YOUTH IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract. This article talks about the focus on youth in Uzbekistan and its historical significance. Proposals are presented on some issues.

Key words: space, time, nation, person, minor.

Introduction

Since the 80s of the XX century, many countries of the world have been living using the economic and technical achievements of globalization. As a result of this, space and time are reduced, and the impenetrable borders between countries are lost, and people enter into deeper, direct and multilateral ties in relation to all eras. At the moment, this circumstance is causing negative phenomena, chunonchi, contacts made with long distances, distancing relationships with loved ones, causing alienation from their offspring. As the world, people and values lose their value, the people are moving away from Brotherhood, national culture, their own history.

As a result, the emergence of an idealized globalization of negative events that pose a threat to the future of their nation, affecting the human population. Using the same situation, various ideological attacks are emerging, in which the consciousness of young people attacks their souls. In the era of such ideological struggles, each country should preserve its younger generation, educate them as people loyal to the interests of the nation and the country, with a selfless, healthy outlook. In this regard, the work carried out in our country is an example for the whole world.

After independence, great positive changes took place in our country, restoring our self-esteem, national statehood, culture, language and religion, national values, and gaining a reputation worthy of ourselves in the Jahan community.

During the years of independence, laws and legislative norms were adopted, which are of great importance for the democratization of all spheres and aspects of our life, for the modernization of the country, for the processes of liberalization of economic and political spheres, and a completely new concept of reforming the judicial system was created in our country. The rise processes in our country are also adequately evaluated by many influential international organizations. The law and legal acts adopted in this regard in our republic, the measures taken, are aimed primarily at raising a healthy and harmonious generation, to form a national pride that embodied universal values within itself.

As we all know, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. On January 7, 2008 at the initiative of Karimov "on guarantees of Child Rights", on April 4 "on ratification of the convention on the smallest age for hiring", on April 8 "on urgent measures to ban and eliminate severe forms of child labor", on April 16 "on amendments and additions to certain laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the improvement of, On July 8, The

Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan"on the Prevention of human trafficking, especially the trade of women and children, and on the ratification of the Protocol on putting an end to it and punishment for it, complementing the UN Convention Against Transnational Organized Crime" were adopted.

The fact that 2016 is declared the Year of a healthy mother and child in our country, in this regard, relevant decisions are being made by our government in the formation of young people as spiritually and physically mature, in their protection from various negative influences, the necessary conditions are being created for young people to actively participate in all spheres of our economy, On February 6, 2014, the" law on youth policy of Uzbekistan " was re-implemented and PQ-2124 was adopted, according to which a program of measures was established that will serve to comprehensively train young people.

On August 12, 2013, the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan discussed the draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the Prevention of Juvenile neglect and delinquency", which was approved by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis in September.

In addition, article 188-2 was introduced into this code, taking into account the proposals made by the Ministry of Internal Affairs regarding amendments and additions to certain articles of the Code of administrative responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

After these changes, in order to prevent minors and young people from aimlessly beating at night, spending time in Internet cafes, nightclubs watching pornographic films that do not correspond to our national identity and mentality (regularly), they conduct special raids and study the activities of these places.

On September 14, 2016, the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on state budget for youth"was adopted. It is in the era of globalization that the importance of this law is very high for the implementation of all changes in the path of development of our country, for the education of young people who are able to become decisive power, support and support for us.

"We will continue our state policy on youth with determination, without any deviation. Not only will we continue, but we will raise this policy as our top priority to the high level that time demands today.

We mobilize all the forces and opportunities of our state and society in order for our youth to be independent-thinking, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, and to be able to mature and be happy as people who do not come to their peers in any field on a global scale."[1] in his words, the essence of state policy aimed at educating the younger generation in our country has found expression.

As a result of the improvement of "State Youth Policy" in Uzbekistan, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.On the initiative of Mirziyoyev, the Youth Union of Uzbekistan was established, and the date of June 30 was declared "Youth Day" in our country. In addition, in the practice of Uzbekistan, a completely new system was created, namely the Institute for the study of special – youth problems and training of promising personnel, which is engaged in the study of various pressing problems of young people. The establishment of this institution under the Academy of Public Administration under the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan was the basis for the formation of scientific-methodical and analytical-research activities of the Institute on the basis of the requirements of the time.

Also, a special emphasis was placed on the issue of establishing the position of young leadership personnel in the field of Public Administration, their training and appointment to various responsible positions. This, as the head of our country noted, found its expression in

the concept of “social lift”. Over the years, a number of young people have been trained in 4-month retraining courses by the Institute for the study of youth problems and the training of promising personnel, and most of them have been appointed to senior positions in ministries, departments and organizations.

Over the past period, the legal basis of the work carried out has also been strengthened. In particular, on the basis of the initiative and practical support of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 40 laws and legislative acts related to youth policy were adopted.

As one of the most important directions in the field of youth policy, our distinguished president on March 19, 2019 launched 5 important initiatives on strengthening attention to youth, their wide involvement in culture, art, physical education and sports, the formation of skills in the use of information technologies in them, the promotion of reading among young people, the approach to issues of increasing Through this, the head of state emphasized that “special attention should be paid to educating our youth in spiritual perfection, protecting them from the influence of various harmful and alien ideas.” It should be noted that such works are among the new mechanisms in the field of Youth Policy and are of great educational importance in terms of their involvement in art, music and sports.

But further improvement of the work in this regard, research of new mechanisms based on the requirements of the time, regular study of the best practices of foreign countries and implementation of methods suitable for the conditions of Uzbekistan and meeting our national characteristics are urgent tasks. Because, in the conditions of globalization, a natural need for new methods and mechanisms is born even in the field of youth policy, when information attacks are accelerated, a struggle is taking place for the minds and hearts of young people, and most importantly, their worldview is changing. When it comes to corruption in education, a thousand unfortunately continue to increase as much as it is fought against it.

In this regard “state youth policy” is also considered important in terms of carrying out the tasks of working with young people in the conditions of Uzbekistan, raising the political, legal consciousness and culture of young people, actively involving them in political processes, developing youth entrepreneurship, improving the financial mechanisms for implementing State Youth Policy, developing scientific and theoretical views, developing easy ways.

In our opinion, during the years of independence, many of our young people are talented, strong-willed, who set clear goals for themselves in our country. But it is necessary to explain that the care and confidence of our people in them, which is now showing our state to young people, should be thoughtful and carry out appropriate activities, become the main activity of every coach and teacher working at every stage of Education. When, in the minds of young people, Uzbekistan becomes a solid belief that only a single Motherland, only a person can be developed in this homeland, that is, ideological immunity is formed, they can justify this confidence with excellent reading, scientific and creative success, the well-being of our ring, selfless work on the path of development of our country and the.

Conclusion

The purpose of the noble works carried out for young people in our country is clear, because the most noble goals we have are the great future of our country, our tomorrow, our free and prosperous life, and what place Uzbekistan occupies in the 21st century from the world community – all this depends, first of all, on what kind of person young people

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